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Lessons-learnt from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations

Deliverable Report

D15.8

WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks

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D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 2

Table of contents

1	Authors and acknowledgements	4
2	Glossary	5
3	Abstract/Summary	6
4	Introduction	7
5	Workshop preparations	9
5.1	Scope and purpose	9
5.2	Participant invitation	9
5.3	Preparation and process for drafting conclusions and recommendations	9
5.4	Pre-workshop webinars	10
6	Workshop ‘Chemical Mixtures: Lessons we are learning from HBM4EU’	11
6.1	Day 1	11
6.2	Day 2	11
6.3	Highlights from the discussions on the draft recommendations	12
6.3.1	Recommendation #1	12
6.3.2	Recommendation #2	12
6.3.3	Recommendation #3	12
6.3.4	Recommendation #4	13
6.3.5	Recommendation #5	13
6.3.6	Recommendation #6	14
6.3.7	Recommendation #7	14
6.3.8	Recommendation #8	14
6.3.9	Recommendation #9	15
6.3.10	Recommendation #11	16
6.3.11	Recommendation #12	16
6.3.12	Recommendation #13	16
6.3.13	Recommendation #14	17
6.3.14	Recommendation #15	17
6.3.15	Recommendation #16	17
6.4	Results from the online poll on draft recommendations	18
7	Conclusions	20
7.1	Overall conclusions	20
7.1.1	Spinoff	20
7.2	Reworded set of (interim) recommendations	21
7.3	Future steps	21
8	References	22

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 3

9	Annexes.....	23
9.1	Annex 1: Preparatory group	23
9.2	Annex 2: Workshop programme	24
9.3	Annex 3: Draft conclusions and recommendations	28
9.4	Annex 4: Results of the poll on draft recommendations	31
9.5	Annex 5: Reworded recommendations	40

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 4

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D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 5

2 Glossary

HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HI	Hazard Index
HQ	Hazard Quotient
MAF	Mixture Assessment Factor
MRA	Mixture Risk Assessment
PFAS	Per- and polyFluoroAlkyl Substances
RPF	Relative Potency Factors
QA/QC	Quality Assurance/Quality Control

D15.8 - Lessons-learnt from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 6

3 Abstract/Summary

With the aim to improve current procedures for mixture risk assessment (MRA) of (environmental) chemicals, various approaches are being investigated within HBM4EU. Based on the insights and lessons learned thus far in the context of HBM4EU, conclusions as well as recommendations for risk assessment of chemical mixtures and for further research have been drafted. In order to discuss the draft recommendations with stakeholders, an online workshop was organised in October 2021. This workshop was preceded by a series of four pre-conference webinars, to share the lessons learnt and sketch the regulatory context. In the workshop, the draft recommendations (sixteen in total) were discussed with various stakeholders.

Overall, there was considerable support and agreement with the spirit, scope and intention of the draft recommendations, although rewordings for many recommendations were suggested. Valuable propositions were received to clarify recommendations and to improve wording. This report aims to describe the lessons learnt through the HBM4EU project and to present the outcomes of the workshop.

D15.8 - Lessons-learnt from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 7

4 Introduction

Risk assessment of chemical mixtures is complex and poses a number of challenges for scientists, risk assessors and risk managers due to the large number of chemicals present in the environment. The issue of mixture risk assessment is high on the agenda, in research as well as in the regulatory and policy arenas. Generic recommendations on future research and policy development have been drawn up earlier. For example, a group of scientists published a Statement on advancing the assessment of chemical mixtures and their risks for human health and the environment (Drakvik et al. 2020).

Also the EU's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (European Commission, 2020a) expresses the ambition to account for the cocktail effect of chemicals when assessing risks from chemicals, with the overall aim to work towards a toxic-free environment. Among others, the Commission aims to introduce or reinforce provisions to take account of the combination effects in relevant legislations, such as legislation on water, food additives, toys, food contact material, detergents and cosmetics.

For REACH, it will be assessed how to best introduce (a) mixture assessment factor(s) for the chemical safety assessment of substances. More details can be found in the accompanying Staff Working Document (European Commission, 2020b), which describes the progress made since 2012 on the assessment of (un)intentional mixtures and to provide background information and evidence base to actions announced in EU's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability.

The HBM4EU project addresses how Human Biomonitoring (HBM) data can contribute to both the science and policy/regulations of dealing with the phenomenon of combined exposure to multiple chemical substances. Within the HBM4EU project, the focus for chemical mixtures is on chemicals with exposure routes through the environment, food, occupation and/or consumer products.

With the aim to improve current procedures for risk assessment of chemical mixtures, various approaches are being investigated within HBM4EU. These include: i) estimating exposure to mixtures through differential network analyses of existing HBM data (Task 15.1); ii) estimating exposure to pesticide mixtures using suspect screening analyses of citizens living in 'hot spot' versus 'control' areas (Task 15.2); and iii) establishing an advanced workflow for assessing mixture health effects (Task 15.3). These activities are carried out by HBM4EU partners working closely together and in dialogue with EU regulatory agencies and similar initiatives in the EU.

While mixtures are high on the research, regulatory and policy agendas, opinions on how to deal with mixture risk problems vary considerably. This became apparent from a first exploratory assessment, carried out in the framework of HBM4EU WP15, of potential information needs from a governance perspective for mixture risk management. In this exercise, a set of questions were used in structured interviews with researchers and policy makers to delineate the current discourse on mixture risk governance.

Information needs on mixtures was operationalised here as "How can we effectively and efficiently manage the health risks associated with chemical mixtures in the European population in such a way that residual mixture risks are considered acceptable from a public health and personal health point of view, while maintaining to the degree possible the societal and personal benefits of the products that lead to the mixture exposures".

One of the main conclusions was that information needs from policy makers and experts are still rather diffuse and unarticulated, in line with the 'systemic risk' nature of mixtures. Thus, consequences for functionality of HBM mixture data cannot directly be derived. Also, views on responsibilities and criteria to guide risk reduction strategies varied considerably. Potential

D15.8 - Lessons-learnt from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 8

problems in cooperation between silo's from different policy domains (like DG's) were seen as mainly stemming from differences in regulations and the absence of a common regulatory framework.

Regarding the recommendations for risk assessment of chemical mixtures and for further research, these were drafted by a team of experts involved in HBM4EU based on the HBM4EU results obtained thus far. The aim was not so much as to reiterate earlier generic recommendations, but to contribute and enrich existing recommendations through information/science-based recommendations drawn directly from HBM4EU. These draft recommendations were discussed in an online workshop held on October 14-15, 2021. The overall aim of this report is to describe the lessons learnt through the HBM4EU project and to present the outcomes of the workshop.

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 9

5 Workshop preparations

5.1 Scope and purpose

The scope of the workshop, defined by a preparatory group (Annex 1), was to discuss the insights and lessons being learned within HBM4EU in relation to risk assessment of chemical mixtures. More specifically, the goal of the workshop was to present a summary of the results obtained from the WP15 tasks and to present and discuss recommendations for further research and for policy development regarding chemical mixtures. This involved, firstly, to share these insights across the partnership and stakeholders involved; then, on these shared and overarching insights, their implications for research and policy development were jointly assessed. Since not all inputs from all tasks could be harvested in time before the workshop, due to COVID-19 implications, some results have a preliminary character. As a consequence, the recommendations in D15.8 still have a preliminary character and an update may be supplied around May 2022 in a hand-over document to PARC.

Based on the scope and purpose of the workshop, the preparatory group developed the workshop programme (Annex 9.2). To facilitate open and frank discussions, the workshop was held in the spirit of the Chatham House Rule¹. The workshop consisted of sessions where researchers presented the highlights of their findings from the respective tasks in WP15, intertwined with presentations from regulatory authorities, i.e. EFSA and ECHA. The draft recommendations were presented in three sessions, followed by discussions on these recommendations in six breakout groups. Each of these breakout groups provided a concise summary of the discussions held in the plenary session. The main outcomes of the discussions are summarised in this report.

5.2 Participant invitation

An invitation to participate in the workshop 'Chemical Mixtures: Lessons we are learning from HBM4EU' was sent out on 7th September 2021 to the HBM4EU WP15 partners, the HBM4EU Management Board (thus covering all other WPs), the members of HBM4EU Policy Board and relevant networks (e.g. partners of the EuroMix follow-up consortium). Overall, >120 people were invited; of these, 92 persons registered.

Registration for the workshop was necessary in order for participants to receive the link to the online workshop, to allow timely circulation of the draft conclusions and recommendations to participants and to invite them to join the pre-workshop webinars (see section 5.4). The participants of the workshop represented a wide group of stakeholders, ranging from the European Commission to academia to NGOs such as ChemTrust.

5.3 Preparation and process for drafting conclusions and recommendations

The preparatory group drafted a set of conclusions and recommendations (Annex **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**) based on the results obtained thus far in HBM4EU, especially from work done in WP15, WP16, WP5, WP8 and WP10. The drafting involved several iterations through teleconferences and e-mail discussions. The draft conclusions and recommendations were also discussed with the HBM4EU Management Board and WP15 partners. Once consensus was achieved, the draft conclusions and recommendations were

¹ Under the **Chatham House Rule**, anyone who comes to a meeting is free to use information from the discussion, but is not allowed to reveal the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s). It is designed to increase openness of discussion.

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 10

circulated to participants prior to the workshop. The draft recommendations were primarily meant to stimulate an open discussion among participants. Moreover, the focus was on conclusions and recommendations that emerge from the HBM4EU project and not on more generic recommendations.

To allow workshop participants to familiarise themselves with the complex material, methodologies and results that emerged from the tasks in WP15 and other WPs, and to share the lessons learnt and to sketch the regulatory context, dedicated pre-workshop webinars were organised.

5.4 Pre-workshop webinars

The goal of the four pre-workshop webinars was to allow workshop participants to familiarise themselves with the complex material, methodologies and results that emerged from the tasks in WP15, and to share the lessons learnt and to sketch the regulatory context. These webinars focused on the key results of the three tasks in WP15, plus the EU's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. The latter topic was added to allow the scientists involved to become familiar with the future policy and regulatory arena of EU's Chemical Strategy for Sustainability that will form the context for future mixture risk assessment and management.

An invitation and programme were sent out to registered workshop participants. Focus in the webinars was on the introduction of the novel methodologies applied and, on the results and conclusions. At the webinars, no recommendations were discussed. Each of the webinars was recorded and links to the recordings were posted at the HBM4EU website (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/training/>).

The four pre-workshop webinars, which were open to HBM4EU partners and involved stakeholders, covered the following subjects:

1. Suspect screening of pesticide mixtures, the SPECIMEn study;
Monday October 4th, 16.00 – 17.00 [link to recording](#)
2. EC's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability; context of mixture risk assessment and management;
Thursday October 7, 11.00-12.00 [link to recording](#)
3. Patterns in real-life exposures to mixtures; results from HBM network analyses in WP15.1;
Friday, 8th October 2021, 11.00- 12.00 h [link to recording](#)
4. Health risk from exposure to mixtures; results from the case studies in WP15.3;
Friday October 8, 14.00-15.00 [link to recording](#)

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 11

6 Workshop ‘Chemical Mixtures: Lessons we are learning from HBM4EU’

6.1 Day 1

On Day 1 (*i.e.* October 14th, 2021) the project HBM4EU, the Work Package 15 on Mixtures and the general scope, purpose and objectives of the workshop were introduced.

Methods, approach and first results of Task 15.2, entitled ‘Suspect screening in SPECIMEn: Joint survey of pesticides’, were summarised in cooperation with WP16. The novel approach of suspect screening in HBM, *i.e.* on pesticides was introduced and the application in a five country study described. First results were presented, mainly for illustration purposes, since the QA/QC process of the suspect screening is still in progress and only a limited number of pesticides (22) has been identified thus far.

After this presentation, the first set of draft recommendations was presented and subsequently discussed in six breakout groups.

The next presentations covered the work of Task 15.3 (‘Identification of mixture health effects’) and presented the results of a selected set of case studies on health effects. The presentation also involved activities under WP5 regarding the derivation of Relative Potency Factors, using the example of PFAS.

The presentation of the Task 15.3 case studies was followed by a presentation on the EFSA perspective on suspect screening analyses and the assessment of health effects of chemical mixtures.

Then, the second set of draft recommendations was presented and discussed in breakout sessions, after which the first day of the workshop was closed.

6.2 Day 2

Day 2 of the workshop (*i.e.* October 15th, 2021) started with a brief reiteration of the scope and purpose of the workshop, for those participants who could not join on day 1. After that, the rapporteurs from the six breakout groups reported on the two discussions sessions of the previous day.

The next presentation regarded Task 15.1 and introduced Network analyses for the identification of relevant mixtures. This started out with an introduction of network analysis methods with illustration from an already published first exercise of the method on existing HBM mixture data (Ottenbros et al, 2021). Also, some preliminary results from ongoing work using other existing HBM mixture data were shown.

This presentation was followed by a special case study executed under Task 15.3, which focused on HBM and measurement error (described in Agier et al, 2020).

Then, the ECHA perspective on the utility of patterns in exposure for chemical risk assessment was presented, followed by the third set of draft recommendations and breakout group discussions.

After the findings from this third discussion session were reported back to the main group, participants were invited to fill in an online Mentimeter poll to report their level of (dis)agreement with the 16 draft recommendations (see below). Finally, a broader plenary discussion ensued on the lessons learned from HBM4EU on mixtures and the implications of the HBM4EU findings.

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 12

6.3 Highlights from the discussions on the draft recommendations

In order to ensure detailed discussions of each of the draft recommendations, three sessions with breakout groups were included in the programme. In these discussion sessions the focus was on the draft recommendations, not on the draft conclusions. In total there were six breakout groups. The main outcomes of the discussions are presented below.

6.3.1 Recommendation #1

‘Implementation of existing methodologies for mixture risk assessment by regulatory agencies should be accelerated, given the HBM4EU observations on mixture exposures and health risks.’

There was general support for the recommendation, but also concern about data availability and legal basis. Also, it is unclear what existing methodologies are referred to, for some this is obvious, for others not. Here also the Mixture Assessment Factor (MAF) was brought into the debate, where some like the non-quantitative methodology and other do not like a MAF due to its generic aspect. Also, without an idea of the numerical value, the discussion of MAF is of limited use here.

Several groups refer to the regulatory context and legal basis of MRA; while this recommendation does not specify this, other recommendations press for a cross-silo approach as the way to deal with unintended mixtures. One of the breakout groups stressed the need for across regulatory sectors approaches. Some rewording was also suggested.

Recommendation #1, v2

‘Implementation of available methodologies for mixture risk assessment by (national and international) regulatory agencies should be accelerated to the degree possible, based on the evidence HBM4EU has generated on mixture exposures and health risks.’

6.3.2 Recommendation #2

‘Mixture-related research should be continued to further develop and implement approaches for risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals.’

While generally the breakout groups supported the expressed intention, the statement was considered too general with limited added value in relation to the other recommendations. Therefore, it was decided to drop this recommendation.

6.3.3 Recommendation #3

‘HBM data, particularly data on the common occurrence of chemicals, need to be more widely utilised, both in design of toxicological mixture studies, epidemiological studies and in risk assessment and management.’

Overall, there was agreement with the recommendation. From the perspective of risk assessment and management, it was mentioned that data availability is an issue. More specifically, in terms of data quality and granularity, *i.e.* availability of observations at the level of the individual, which is restricted through GDPR. Another consideration is that the toxicological mixture studies should not comprise *in vivo* studies, in view of ethical considerations.

Recommendation #3, v2

‘HBM data of appropriate quality and granularity, particularly data on the common occurrence of chemicals, need to be more widely utilised, both in design of toxicological mixture studies, epidemiological studies and in risk assessment and management.’

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 13

6.3.4 Recommendation #4

'A strategy for the measurement of multiple exposure and effect biomarkers in the same subject in HBM programmes needs to be developed. This requires the development of an inclusive HBM/exposome infrastructure in Europe.'

Generally, the breakout groups agreed with the recommendation. One group questioned whether effect biomarkers are 'at the same level' as exposure biomarkers and are sufficiently developed to include in HBM programmes. That being said, HBM4EU already worked on effect biomarkers and several HBM programmes and exposome projects already utilise effect biomarkers on a large scale.

It was also brought up that collection of auxiliary information on exposure routes, e.g. from questionnaires or indoor measurement would also be part of such a strategy. The question was raised whether it is feasible to always assess multiple exposures. This is not implied in a strategy to always measure. The strategy would consist of conscious consideration of the added value of measuring multiple biomarkers in the same individual versus the additional costs. It is reasonable to expect that measurement of wide array multiple biomarkers would happen in subgroups and not per se in all individuals or all HBM media collected.

The breakout groups also agreed on the need for appropriate infrastructure. EIRENE, the EU research infrastructure on human exposome (environmental determinants of health) developed under ESFRI was seen as a step in the right direction.

Recommendation #4, v2

'A strategy for the measurement of multiple exposure and effect biomarkers in the same subject in HBM programmes needs to be developed, building on the HBM4EU experience. This requires the development of an inclusive HBM/exposome infrastructure in Europe.'

6.3.5 Recommendation #5

'Sensitivity analysis of the impact of MAF (e.g. 5, 10, 100) should be applied in further research at the level of identified mixture communities from network analyses, the SPECIMEn study as well as the case studies, to gauge what resulting HBM levels and thus co-occurring exposures would be under application of a MAF. Valuable data from other WPs in HBM4EU should be considered as well.'

Most breakout groups thought that this recommendation was unclear and needed rewording. Various opinions about a MAF were expressed; there was general agreement that the value of a MAF should be science-based and data driven. Overall, people agreed that, although HBM4EU has not directly looked at a MAF, building on the HBM4EU (mixture) data and experience, including the cases studies, would add value to the derivation of an appropriate MAF.

In particular, through simulation studies and sensitivity analyses, the consequences of a MAF on ensuing mixture exposures and HBM mixture levels could be assessed through data from e.g. the HBM4EU network analysis on existing data and on SPECIMEn data combined with experience of the cases studies. Moreover, the impact of a MAF on mixture risk reduction could be gauged in this way. Since this activity is not part of the HBM4EU workplans, extra effort is needed, to inform the debate and decision making on a MAF in a timely fashion.

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 14

Recommendation #5, v2

'HBM4EU (mixture) data and experience should be applied to support the science-based derivation of an appropriate Mixture Assessment Factor (MAF). Simulation studies and sensitivity analyses, using HBM4EU (mixture) data, cases studies and overall experience would allow to assess consequences of a MAF on ensuing mixture exposures and HBM mixture levels, as well as gauge the impact of a MAF on the resulting mixture risk reduction.'

6.3.6 Recommendation #6

'Further research should focus on refinement of approaches to identify real-life chemical mixtures to which the population is exposed and how to prioritise the mixtures of concern.'

Overall, there was agreement with the scope and intention of the recommendation. However, further specification was needed, particularly with regard to the intended approaches. Additionally, it was suggested to reword the recommendation for making the link between the scientific evidence and the support to policy making. Also, incorporation of toxicological potency information, grouping of chemicals according to their toxicological mode of action and the drivers of toxicity should be included. This resulted in the following modification.

Recommendation #6, v2

'Further research should focus on broadening and refinement of a combination of approaches to identify real-life chemical mixtures of concern to which the population is exposed. This will allow prioritisation of mixtures of concern and support policy decisions. This involves data-driven approaches and methodologies to incorporate toxicological potency information and to group substances with common modes of action.'

6.3.7 Recommendation #7

'In the absence of sufficiently detailed information of pesticide use, it is recommended to apply pesticide suspect screening to identify similar pesticide uses across different countries that merit further targeted analysis.'

In general participants of the breakout groups agreed with the intention and scope of the recommendation, to support and promote suspect/non-targeted screening analysis. However, it was suggested to broaden the recommendation beyond pesticides, to avoid the impression that other chemicals may not merit further analysis. In addition, it should be specified that suspect screening is on human samples.

Recommendation #7, v2

'When data on substance use and exposures is limited, it is recommended to apply suspect screening analysis in human samples to get a broader overview and a semi-quantitative evaluation of substance exposures across the EU. This will allow prioritisation of substances for targeted analysis and comparison of the suspect screening data with reported substance usage.'

6.3.8 Recommendation #8

'Future HBM studies should aim to collect data on the full range of chemicals of interest in sufficiently large study populations, to assess the actual mixture exposures in the population. Semi-quantitative identification through suspect screening and untargeted analysis of chemicals/metabolites can be instrumental to prioritise candidate substances for more targeted quantitative analysis. To this end, quantitative multi-biomarker methods should be developed and used covering 100(s) of biomarkers in HBM studies, in case analytical standards are available.'

While the breakout groups generally agreed with the intention of the statement, some concerns about the feasibility and logistic consequences were expressed. Not all HBM studies would have

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 15

the resources to execute suspect/non-targeted and/or targeted analysis on a wide scale. Particularly for suspect screening analysis careful selection of and focus on relevant suspects is needed. Other considerations were also mentioned, e.g. to include chemicals from different regulatory domains; the added value for hotspots to prioritise further targeted analysis, the ability to address time trends and study replacement and emerging chemicals. While not explicitly stated in the wording of the recommendation, the full range of chemicals of interest should be measured in the same individuals, to allow assessment of co-occurrence. Shortening of the recommendation was also suggested.

Recommendation #8, v2

‘Future HBM studies should aim to collect data on the full range of chemicals of interest by targeted analysis in sufficiently large study populations measured in the same individuals, to assess the actual mixture exposures in the population and co-occurrence in the body.’

6.3.9 Recommendation #9

‘Existing samples collected within the HBM4EU WP8 framework should be re-analysed through suspect screening and untargeted analysis on the full range of chemicals of interest, to broaden and expand the assessment of the actual mixture exposures in the population.’

Across the breakout groups various issues were raised. Nevertheless, there was agreement with the intention of the recommendation. However, expansion to other HBM data sources (e.g. DEMOCOPHES) was suggested. Also, the feasibility of using existing samples was questioned, for various reasons, including analytical and methodological reasons as well as the representativeness of existing samples. Therefore, it was suggested to consider collecting new samples for suspect screening analyses, for example in the context of PARC. Furthermore, suggestions were made to look at time trends, e.g. to monitor exposure to substitutes. Based on the discussion, a new version of the recommendation was drafted:

Recommendation #9, v2

‘Existing samples collected within the HBM4EU WP8 framework and earlier relevant HBM studies should be screened on feasibility aspects for re-analysis through suspect screening and untargeted analysis. This will allow to expand the assessment of actual mixture exposures in the population and to assess time trends.’

Recommendation #10

‘Methodologies for mixture risk assessment by regulatory agencies should also include approaches for the identification of risk drivers, with the aim to facilitate risk management.’

There was general agreement with the statement, but also several ‘ifs and buts’ about practicalities were raised. The role of risk drivers that contribute most to the mixture risk may change over time due to replacements of chemicals. On the other hand, diffuse exposures to persistent legacy chemicals may act as risk drivers, but may be difficult to further manage.

Recommendation #10, v2

‘Methodologies for mixture risk assessment by regulatory agencies and authorities should also include approaches for the identification of risk drivers that contribute most to the mixture risk, with the aim to focus and facilitate risk management.’

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 16

6.3.10 Recommendation #11

'In the risk assessment of new chemicals, pre-existing exposures to legacy compounds that produce similar adverse outcomes need to be taken into account.'

The wording of this recommendation was thought to be insufficiently clear, with confusion about the meaning of 'new', 'pre-existing exposures' and 'legacy compounds'. While there was agreement with the intention of the recommendation, i.e. to consider existing mixture exposures and body burdens, in risk assessments, clarification and rewording was proposed.

Also, concerns about the practical feasibility were raised. It was also noted that pre-existing exposures and body burdens originate from different regulatory silos, which brings about further challenges. Also, the available data may not always allow for this. Information on the toxicokinetics are also considered relevant here.

The issue was raised whether old existing chemicals on the market should be treated more lenient than new ones, because previous risk assessments did not consider co-exposures and body burdens? What would be the implication in the situation of a new chemical authorisation, where body burdens of metals like lead, or cadmium, or persistent organic pollutants would already have a hazard index above or close to 1. Would new chemicals be restricted because this would further increase the hazard index above 1?

Recommendation #11, v2

'In the risk assessment for the authorisation of a new chemical, existing mixture exposures and body burdens of substances with similar adverse outcomes, need to be taken into account to the degree possible.'

6.3.11 Recommendation #12

'The observation of non-compliance of some chemicals with their single regulatory values should guide risk management measures, but should not distract from the need to tackle the mixtures problem. A focus on dealing with non-compliant chemicals should not delay speedy adoption of mixture risk assessment strategies.'

Between breakout groups there was some variation of opinions on this recommendation. Several groups agreed with the intention, while another thought that the first sentence only stated the obvious and therefore could be deleted. Some clarification of wording was also suggested.

It was noted that most chemicals are not regulated and therefore there is no 'non-compliance' with regulations. Also, that focus on drivers of toxicity would be more efficient than addressing the whole mixture (note that you would only know those drivers if you first knew the whole mixture).

Recommendation #12, v2

'Compliance or non-compliance of some chemicals with their single regulatory values should not distract from their possible contribution to mixture problems/risks.'

6.3.12 Recommendation #13

'Interpretation of results from the Hazard Index approach should be done with great care, when assessment factors vary substantially.'

Overall, there was agreement with the intention of the recommendation. It was stressed that the HI approach is a simple low tier approach where conservative assessment factors are being applied. Interpretation of HI should always be done with great care, taken into account uncertainty and the origin and precise nature of the applied assessment factors used to derive individual substance

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 17

HQs, even when they do not vary substantially across substances. A PODI approach would be more robust in that sense.

It was also suggested to use distribution of assessment factors to capture the underlying uncertainty and to initiate further research on development of scientific criteria for selecting assessment factors.

Recommendation #13, v2

‘In the interpretation of results from the Hazard Index in a tiered approach, sufficient attention should be given to the underlying uncertainties in the applied assessment factors for the substance-specific Hazard Quotients used in the Hazard Index.’

6.3.13 Recommendation #14

‘In the risk assessment of mixtures, chemicals from other sources, e.g. medication or recreational drugs, that produce similar adverse outcomes, should also be taken into account.’

While there was overall agreement, the practical feasibility is a concern, as is the current absence of a legal basis to do so. Both the delineation as well as the practice of risk assessment varies across regulatory silos and for medication risk/benefit considerations also play a different role, as do (in)voluntariness of the exposures.

Two groups stressed that this is the whole point of addressing unintentional mixtures. Others indicated that not so much the risk assessment, but the risk management of mixtures is the issue.

Recommendation #14, v2

‘In the risk assessment and management of mixtures, chemicals from other sources, e.g. medication or recreational drugs, that produce similar adverse outcomes, should also be taken into account to the degree possible. A legal basis to do so needs to be further developed.’

6.3.14 Recommendation #15

‘The results of the network analysis underscore the need to strengthen mixture risk assessment across regulatory domains and sectors, as also stated by Kortenkamp and Faust (2018) and Drakvik et al (2020).’

Overall, breakout groups agreed, but mentioned repetitiveness with other recommendations, the pivotal role of risk management, the need of knowledge about exposure, exposure routes and source contributions. Also, it is not the tool of network analysis *per se*, but the groups of co-occurring chemicals of high toxicological concern should be prioritised.

Recommendation #15, v2

‘The identification of groups of co-occurring substances, regulated in different domains and sector, and of toxicological concern, as through network analysis and mixture risk assessment, underscores the need to strengthen mixture risk assessment across regulatory domains and sectors.’

6.3.15 Recommendation #16

‘Continuation of the predominant single-chemical approach in risk assessment implies that single chemicals are released into an otherwise chemically pristine environment, an absurd assumption as there is exposure to multiple other co-occurring chemicals. Thus, risk assessments of chemicals should embrace the assessment of co-occurring multiple chemical exposures.’

While there was general agreement with the intention, rewording and shortening was suggested, since the first part, while true and obvious to many, is not a recommendation. Also, overlap with

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 18

other recommendations was mentioned. One breakout group extended the discussion to the role of the MAF. Given the changes made to the other recommendations, it was decided to drop this recommendation.

6.4 Results from the online poll on draft recommendations

In addition to the discussion sessions, a Mentimeter poll was held with the aim to get an impression about the extent to which participants of the workshop agree with the intention and scope of the recommendations drafted.

The Mentimeter poll consisted of shortened versions of the 16 draft recommendations. The shortening was necessary since topics had a maximum size of 150 characters. Below the main (shortened) text, the original text of the recommendation was presented in a smaller font to allow direct comparison. Participants filled out the poll at their own pace.

A total of 43 participants have responded to the online poll. Table 6.4.1 summarises the scores obtained from the participants.

Table 6.4: Level of (dis)agreement with formulated recommendations in the poll (n=43)

Recommendation number	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Average
1.	2	0	1	23	17	1.2
2.	1	0	3	13	26	1.5
3.	0	1	2	24	16	1.3
4.	0	0	5	17	21	1.4
5.	0	4	16	20	3	0.5
6.	0	1	4	16	22	1.4
7.	0	3	17	14	9	0.7
8. a	0	2	3	11	27	1.5
b	0	1	10	24	8	0.9
c	0	1	8	26	8	1.0
9.	2	5	14	17	5	0.4
10.	0	1	4	20	18	1.3
11.	0	0	9	17	17	1.2
12.	0	0	4	23	16	1.3
13.	0	0	11	23	9	1.0
14.	1	1	5	17	19	1.2
15.	0	2	7	18	16	1.1
16.						

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 19

Overall, there was generally good agreement with the presented recommendations, with few participants (strongly) disagreeing with the recommendations (Annex 4). All recommendations had positive average scores, most above 1. Only one recommendation (no. 9 regarding re-analysis of the HBM4EU samples from WP8 by suspect screening and non-targeted screening) had two 'Strongly disagree' votes. Still, the average score for this recommendation was 0.4. Thus, there was general consensus among participants from science as well as policy makers and other stakeholders.

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 20

7 Conclusions

7.1 Overall conclusions

With over 90 registered participants, there was considerable interest in the topic of the workshop and broad representation from researchers, policy makers and stakeholders. After presentations, as well as in the breakout sessions, participants actively engaged in constructive discussions.

Overall, there was considerable support and agreement with the spirit, scope and intention of the draft recommendations, although rewordings for many recommendations were suggested. Valuable propositions were received to clarify recommendations and to improve wording.

The general support appeared from the breakout discussions, the plenary back-reports of breakout groups and the Mentimeter poll administered in the final session of the workshop.

In the final general discussion, participants were invited to propose additional recommendations pertinent to the scope of the workshop. A few suggestions were put forward. However, none of these were grounded in HBM4EU results or lessons learnt.

7.1.1 Spinoff

The workshop generated several spinoffs; the pre-workshop webinars were well-attended with 92 participants. Recordings of the four webinars are posted on the HBM4EU website.

The invitations to the workshop also triggered discussion with JRC on the use of public HBM information e.g. from IPCHEM to assess possible values for a MAF. These discussions initiated further cooperation between JRC and HBM4EU partners, and resulted in outreach to Woods Consulting because of their work on the MAF and in the drafting of a letter to DG ENV about the utility of HBM4EU results for the derivation of a science-based MAF.

7.1.1.1 Spinoff in breakout group discussions

Although not strictly warranted from now available HBM4EU data or results, the possible use and added value of a MAF for mixture risk management came up in the discussions. Some participants expressed concerns about the generic character of a MAF. Others considered the MAF as essential and as the only regulatory advance in 30 years of discussions about risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures. Concerns were expressed about the seemingly tight timeframe in which the EC wants to make decisions on a MAF, without allowing sufficient time for a science-based derivation, using existing information, also from earlier HBM studies and from available HBM4EU data.

Opinions expressed and questions raised (but not answered) included:

- The generic non-quantitative aspect of a MAF versus more quantitative approaches such as for pesticides
- What numerical value would a MAF have?
- What would be the scope of application of a MAF in risk assessment and management? Would it involve only new chemicals that enter the market or all new chemicals (but possibly not marketed) or only specific subgroups?
- Would a MAF 'favour' existing chemicals and 'punish' new chemicals entering the market?
- What impact a MAF would have on allowed levels of substances in different exposure media and in resulting HBM levels?
- What is the science-base for a MAF and is the science-base sufficiently utilised, or will arbitrary values for a MAF be implemented?

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 21

- The MAF should be developed on the basis of risk distribution for each chemical
- Since all chemicals have the same probability of co-occurrence, a MAF should be assigned to all chemicals
- Would risk assessors need to apply a MAF or should they supply information to risk managers to support a MAF?

Another topic that come up multiple times in breakout group discussions was the issue of the cost-effectiveness of mixture measurements, e.g. in exposure media and routes and through HBM. Since levels vary considerably in time and space, a good assessment of mixture exposure levels requires relatively dense measurement networks and thus are costly. Is it efficient to measure multiple chemicals in the same samples, through targeted measurement, suspect screening or non-targeted analysis? Or should risk managers apply generic approaches that are not data-driven? Opinions amongst participants on this issue varied, mostly along the lines of scientists versus regulators/policy makers.

7.2 Reworded set of (interim) recommendations

Based on the discussions and feedback from the workshop the draft recommendations were adapted and reworded. Two out of the 16 recommendations drafted were dropped because of overlap with other recommendations. Note that the resulting set of fourteen recommendations, for the time being, have an 'interim' character, since not all HBM4EU results are available at this time due to pandemic-related delays. Annex 9.5 lists the reworded version of the interim recommendations.

7.3 Future steps

In the Spring of 2022, the new results of HBM4EU pertinent to mixtures will be evaluated to address to what degree conclusions and recommendations need to be expanded, amended or revised. This mainly involves results from the network analyses (Task 15.1) and the joint survey of pesticides (Task 15.2). This work will be performed by the WP15 participants in cooperation with the HBM4EU Management Board. When substantial revisions would be needed, an additional workshop to address these revisions may be necessary. After a revision, the deliverable D15.8 will be adapted and published as a public deliverable. A scientific publication is also considered.

Results will also be presented at HBM4EU's final workshop. A handover session to the PARC community is anticipated.

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 22

8 References

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D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 23

9 Annexes

9.1 Annex 1: Preparatory group

The workshop and preparatory webinars were prepared by:

- Mirjam Luijten (RIVM)
- Erik Lebret (RIVM/IRAS)
- Jelle Vlaanderen (IRAS)
- Andreas Kortenkamp (BRUNEL)
- Panu Rantakokko (THL)
- Robert Barouki (INSERM)

together with

- Wieneke Bil (RIVM)
- Jacob van Klaveren (RIVM)
- Marcel Mengelers (RIVM)
- Ilse Ottenbros (IRAS/RIVM)
- Shalene den Braver (RIVM)
- Annick van den Brand (RIVM)

D15.8 - Lessons-learnt from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 24

9.2 Annex 2: Workshop programme

HBM4EU Workshop

‘Chemical Mixtures: Lessons we are learning from HBM4EU’

Virtual, 14-15 October 2021

Organisers: Mirjam Luijten (RIVM), Erik Leuret (RIVM), Jelle Vlaanderen (IRAS), Andreas Kortenkamp (BRUNEL) and Robert Barouki (INSERM)

Risk assessment of chemical mixtures is complex and poses a number of challenges for scientists, risk assessors and managers, due to the large number of chemicals present in the environment. The HBM4EU project addresses how Human Biomonitoring (HBM) data can contribute to both the science and policy/regulation of dealing with the phenomenon of mixtures. Within the HBM4EU project, the focus for chemical mixtures is on chemicals with exposure routes through the environment, food, occupation and/or consumer products.

With the aim to improve current procedures for risk assessment of chemical mixtures, various approaches are being investigated within HBM4EU. These include: i) estimating exposure to mixtures through differential network analyses of existing HBM data, ii) estimating exposure to pesticide mixtures using suspect screening analyses of citizens living in ‘hot spot’ versus ‘control’ areas, and iii) establishing an advanced workflow for assessing mixture health effects. These activities are carried out by HBM4EU partners working closely together and in dialogue with EU regulatory agencies and similar initiatives in the EU. Based on the results obtained thus far, recommendations for risk assessment of chemical mixtures and for further research have been drafted.

The overall aim of the workshop is to discuss recommendations for further research and for policy development regarding chemical mixtures, using the insights and lessons being learned within HBM4EU. This involves, firstly, to share these insights across the partnership and stakeholders involved; then, on these shared and overarching insights, their implications for research and policy development can be jointly assessed.

The recommendations will be outlined in D15.8 ‘Report on policy recommendations and future research avenues on mixtures’. Since not all inputs from all tasks could be harvested in time due to COVID-19 implications, some mock data may need to be used. As a consequence, the recommendations in D15.8 may have a preliminary character and an update may be supplied around May 2022 in a hand-over document to PARC.

To share the lessons learnt and sketch the regulatory context, a series of four pre-conference webinars are foreseen, open to HBM4EU partners and involved stakeholders. These involve:

Patterns in real-life exposures to mixtures; results from network analyses in WP15.1

Health risk from exposure to mixtures; results from the case studies in WP15.3

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 25

Suspect screening of mixtures; results from the SPECIMEn pesticide study in WP15.2

EC's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability; context of mixture risk assessment and management

In the online workshop, covering two half-day sessions, and following the webinars, results from the WP15 tasks will be summarised and draft recommendations prepared by WP15 leadership and Pillar 3 leader will be presented and discussed in three discussion sessions. We aim for an interactive workshop, with both plenary and break-out sessions.

The focus will be on improvements to mixture risk assessment that are considered achievable on the short-term and contribute to improved and more efficient protection of human health. Also, a more long-term perspective will be drawn. The workshop will be held in the spirit of the Chatham House Rule², to facilitate open and frank discussions. The outcomes of this workshop will not only be captured in D15.8 but will also be submitted for publication to a peer-reviewed journal.

² Under the **Chatham House Rule**, anyone who comes to a meeting is free to use information from the discussion, but is not allowed to reveal the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker (s). It is designed to increase openness of discussion.

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 26

Programme

Thursday October 14th;

chaired by Erik Lebret (RIVM/IRAS)

- 12.45 – 13.00 Joining the online platform
- 13.00 – 13.05 Welcome; short introduction to HBM4EU to stakeholders – Robert Barouki (INSERM)
- 13.05 – 13.15 Goals of the workshop, expectations and limitations – Mirjam Luijten (RIVM)
- 13.15 – 13.55 Suspect screening in SPECIMEn: Joint survey of pesticides – Jean-Philippe Antignac (INRAE) & Ilse Ottenbros (IRAS/RIVM)
- 13.55 – 14.10 Chemical mixtures: draft recommendations from HBM4EU, session 1 – Mirjam Luijten (RIVM)
- 14.10 – 14.55 Guided discussion on recommendations, session 1 – Breakout groups
- 14.55 – 15.05 Coffee break
- 15.05 – 16.05 Health risk from exposure to mixtures; Case studies on health effects – Andreas Kortenkamp (BRUNEL), Marcel Mengelers (RIVM), Wieneke Bil (RIVM)
- 16.05 – 16.25 EFSA perspective on suspect screening analyses and the assessment of health effects of chemical mixtures – Jean Lou Dorne (EFSA)
- 16.25 – 16.40 Chemical mixtures: draft recommendations from HBM4EU, session 2 – Marcel Mengelers (RIVM)
- 16.40 – 17.25 Guided discussion on recommendations, session 2 – Breakout groups
- 17.25 – 17.30 Wrap up Day 1 – Mirjam Luijten (RIVM)

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 27

Friday October 15th;

chaired by Robert Barouki (INSERM)

- 08.45 – 09.00 Joining the online platform
- 09.00 – 09.05 Goal of day 2 – Erik Lebret (RIVM/IRAS)
- 09.05 – 09.25 Reporting back of breakout sessions Day 1
- 09.25 – 09.45 Network analyses for the identification of relevant mixtures – Jelle Vlaanderen (IRAS)
- 09.45 – 10.05 HBM and measurement error – Rémy Slama (INSERM)
- 10.05 – 10.15 ECHA perspective on utility of patterns in exposure – Fleur van Broekhuizen (ECHA)
- 10.15 – 10.25 Coffee break
- 10.25 – 10.40 Chemical mixtures: draft recommendations from HBM4EU, session 3 – Erik Lebret (RIVM/IRAS)
- 10.40 – 11.25 Guided discussion on recommendations, session 3 – Breakout groups
- 11.25 – 12.30 Lessons learned from HBM4EU on mixtures; what are the implications of the HBM4EU findings?
- 12.30 – 12.40 Wrap up and closure – Mirjam Luijten (RIVM)

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 28

9.3 Annex 3: Draft conclusions and recommendations

Draft conclusions and draft preliminary recommendations on HBM4EU WP15 Mixture activities

The recommendations are preliminary in nature, primarily intended to stimulate open discussions during the HBM4EU WP15 Workshop, 14-15th October 2021

1. Conclusions

Generic

1. Mixtures matter: the different activities conducted in HBM4EU clearly indicate that chemical mixtures pose a concern regarding human health.
2. HBM4EU results show that Human Biomonitoring (HBM) data has the potential of being an instrument to obtain insight into the real-life mixtures the human population is exposed to.
3. While HBM4EU activities did not specifically address the Mixture Assessment Factor (MAF), the results from WP15 and other WPs as well as the data generated in the aligned studies can contribute substantially to a scientific underpinning of the MAF; however, this requires further work.

Exposure

1. Network analysis of existing Human Biomonitoring studies reveal that combined exposures to multiple chemicals are common and occur in all population groups
2. Network analysis of existing Human Biomonitoring studies shows clusters of co-occurring chemicals; chemicals in these mixture clusters are regulated independently under different legislative frameworks.
3. Analysis of existing HBM mixture data demonstrates clusters of co-occurring chemicals showing that the general environment cannot be considered as pristine and leads to body burdens of mixtures.
4. The number of individuals with HBM data for a wide array of chemicals is still relatively scarce due to logistic and financial reasons. Most chemicals are measured in subpopulations and in different media, most in urine, fewer in blood. Thus, the number of individuals with a 'complete HBM data set' is relatively small in comparison with the number of chemicals measured. This may limit the stability/consistency of the network communities identified through network analysis. And thus, our ability to identify mixture exposure patterns of concern.
5. Logistic and financial limitations have prevented HBM4EU new data collections to cover the full range of priority substances to be measured in the same individuals. Different chemical families were measured in different subpopulations, thus none of the individuals studied in WP8 have data on the full range of priority substances.
6. National information on active ingredients of pesticide use per crop type is insufficiently available for a multi-country comparison on pesticide exposures.

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 29

Health effects

1. HBM4EU case studies focused on human health effects clearly show that chemical mixtures are of public health concern. In the majority of the cases it was possible to identify risk drivers, i.e. chemicals that contribute more strongly than others to the health risk.
2. HBM4EU case studies on health effects identified several legacy compounds as important drivers of risks. Network analyses showed that several of such legacy compounds cluster with other newer chemicals.
3. HBM4EU case studies showed that when assessment factors of chemicals combined in a Hazard Index, vary widely the application of a Hazard Index becomes problematic; in such cases the use of the Point of Departure Index is more straight forward.
4. HBM4EU case studies revealed that exposure to some chemicals (primarily legacy chemicals) already exceed their single acceptable levels.

2. Recommendations

Generic

1. Implementation of existing methodologies for mixture risk assessment by regulatory agencies should be accelerated, given the HBM4EU observations on mixture exposures and health risks.
2. Mixture-related research should be continued to further develop and implement approaches for risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals.
3. HBM data, particularly data on the common occurrence of chemicals, need to be more widely utilised, both in design of toxicological mixture studies, epidemiological studies and in risk assessment and management.
4. A strategy for the measurement of multiple exposure and effect biomarkers in the same subject in HBM programmes needs to be developed. This requires the development of an inclusive HBM/exposome infrastructure in Europe.
5. Sensitivity analysis of the impact of MAF (e.g. 5, 10, 100) should be applied in further research at the level of identified mixture communities from network analyses, the SPECIMEn study as well as the case studies, to gauge what resulting HBM levels and thus co-occurring exposures would be under application of a MAF. Valuable data from other WPs in HBM4EU should be considered as well.

Exposure

1. Further research should focus on refinement of approaches to identify real-life chemical mixtures to which the population is exposed and how to prioritise the mixtures of concern.
2. in the absence of sufficiently detailed information of pesticide use, it is recommended to apply pesticide suspect screening to identify similar pesticide uses across different countries that merit further targeted analysis
3. Future HBM studies should aim to collect data on the full range of chemicals of interest in sufficiently large study populations, to assess the actual mixture exposures in the population. Semi-quantitative identification through suspect screening and untargeted analysis of chemicals/metabolites can be instrumental to prioritise candidate substances for more targeted quantitative analysis. To this end, quantitative multi-biomarker methods should be developed and used covering 100(s) of biomarkers in HBM studies, in case analytical standards are available.
4. Existing samples collected within the HBM4EU WP8 framework should be re-analysed through suspect screening and untargeted analysis on the full range of chemicals of

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 30

interest, to broaden and expand the assessment of the actual mixture exposures in the population.

Health risks

1. Methodologies for mixture risk assessment by regulatory agencies should also include approaches for the identification of risk drivers, with the aim to facilitate risk management.
2. In the risk assessment of new chemicals, pre-existing exposures to legacy compounds that produce similar adverse outcomes need be taken into account.
3. The observation of non-compliance of some chemicals with their single regulatory values should guide risk management measures, but should not distract from the need to tackle the mixtures problem. A focus on dealing with non-compliant chemicals should not delay speedy adoption of mixture risk assessment strategies.
4. Interpretation of results from the Hazard Index approach should be done with great care, when assessment factors vary substantially
5. In the risk assessment of mixtures, chemicals from other sources, e.g. medication or recreational drugs, that produce similar adverse outcomes, should also be taken into account.
6. The results of the network analysis underscore the need to strengthen mixture risk assessment across regulatory domains and sectors, as also stated by Kortenkamp and Faust (2018) and Drakvik et al (2020).
7. Continuation of the predominant single-chemical approach in risk assessment implies that single chemicals are released into an otherwise chemically pristine environment, an absurd assumption as there is exposure to multiple other co-occurring chemicals. Thus, risk assessments of chemicals should embrace the assessment of co-occurring multiple chemical exposures.

9.4 Annex 4: Results of the poll on draft recommendations

1: Implementation of existing methods for mixture RA by regulatory agencies should be accelerated, given the HBM4EU observations on mixtures

2: Mixture-related research should be continued to further develop and implement approaches for RA of combined exposure to multiple chemicals.

3: HBM data on common occurrence of chemicals need to be more widely utilised, both in design of toxicological and epi studies and in RA / RM.

4: We need a strategy to measure multiple exposure/effect biomarkers in the same subject in HBM programmes & an inclusive HBM/exposome infrastructure.

5: HBM4EU data should be used in a sensitivity analysis of the impact of MAF to gauge what resulting HBM levels & co-occurring exposures would be.

6: Further research should focus on refinement of approaches to identify real-life chemical mixtures and how to prioritize the mixtures of concern.

7: Without info on pesticide use, suspect screening should be applied to identify similar pesticide uses across countries for targeted analysis.

8.1: Future HBM studies should collect data on the full range of chemicals of interest in large enough study populations to assess the actual mixtures

8.2: Semi-quantitative identification by suspect screening of chemicals is key to prioritize candidate substances for targeted quantitative analysis

8.3: Quantitative multi-biomarker methods should be developed covering 100(s) of biomarkers in HBM studies, where analytical standards are available.

9: Existing HBM4EU WP8 samples should be re-analysed through SS and NTS, to broaden and expand the assessment of the actual mixture exposures.

10: Methods for mixture RA by regulatory agencies should include approaches for the identification of risk drivers, to facilitate risk management.

11: In the RA of new chemicals, pre-existing exposures to legacy compounds that produce similar adverse outcomes need be taken into account.

12: Non-compliance of chemicals with their single regulatory values should guide RM measures but should not delay fast adoption of mixture RA strategy

13: Interpretation of results from the Hazard Index approach should be done with great care, when assessment factors vary substantially

14: In the RA of mixtures, chemicals from other sources, e.g. medication or recreational drugs, with similar adverse outcomes, should be included.

15: The results of the network analysis underscores the need to strengthen mixture RA across regulatory domains and sectors.

16: RAs of chemicals should involve co-occurring multiple chemical exposures; single-chemical approach in RA falsely assumes a pristine environment.

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 40

9.5 Annex 5: Reworded recommendations

The sixteen draft recommendations were adapted and reworded, based on the discussions and feedback from the workshop. Two recommendations were dropped because of overlap with other recommendations. Note that the resulting set of fourteen recommendations listed below have, for the time being, an 'interim' character, since not all HBM4EU results are available at this time due to pandemic-related delays.

1. Implementation of available methodologies for mixture risk assessment by (national and international) regulatory agencies should be accelerated to the degree possible, based on the evidence HBM4EU has generated on mixture exposures and health risks.
2. HBM data of appropriate quality and granularity, particularly data on the common occurrence of chemicals, need to be more widely utilised, both in design of toxicological mixture studies, epidemiological studies and in risk assessment and management.
3. A strategy for the measurement of multiple exposure and effect biomarkers in the same subject in HBM programmes needs to be developed, building on the HBM4EU experience. This requires the development of an inclusive HBM/exposome infrastructure in Europe.
4. HBM4EU (mixture) data and experience should be applied to support the science-based derivation of an appropriate Mixture Assessment Factor (MAF). Simulation studies and sensitivity analyses, using HBM4EU (mixture) data, cases studies and overall experience would allow to assess consequences of a MAF on ensuing mixture exposures and HBM mixture levels, as well as gauge the impact of a MAF on the resulting mixture risk reduction.
5. Further research should focus on broadening and refinement of a combination of approaches to identify real-life chemical mixtures of concern to which the population is exposed. This will allow prioritisation of mixtures of concern and support policy decisions. This involves data-driven approaches and methodologies to incorporate toxicological potency information and to group substances with common modes of action.
6. When data on substance use and exposures is limited, it is recommended to apply suspect screening analysis in human samples to get a broader overview and a semi-quantitative evaluation of substance exposures across the EU. This will allow prioritisation of substances for targeted analysis and comparison of the suspect screening data with reported substance usage.
7. Future HBM studies should aim to collect data on the full range of chemicals of interest by targeted analysis in sufficiently large study populations measured in the same individuals, to assess the actual mixture exposures in the population and co-occurrence in the body.
8. Existing samples collected within the HBM4EU WP8 framework and earlier relevant HBM studies should be screened on feasibility aspects for re-analysis through suspect screening and untargeted analysis. This will allow to expand the assessment of actual mixture exposures in the population and to assess time trends.
9. Methodologies for mixture risk assessment by regulatory agencies and authorities should also include approaches for the identification of risk drivers that contribute most to the mixture risk, with the aim to focus and facilitate risk management.
10. In the risk assessment for the authorisation of a new chemical, existing mixture exposures and body burdens of substances with similar adverse outcomes, need to be taken in account to the degree possible.
11. Compliance or non-compliance of some chemicals with their single regulatory values should not distract from their possible contribution to mixture problems/risks.

D15.8 - Lessons-learned from HBM4EU WP15 on mixtures: intermediate recommendations	Security: Public
WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks	Version: 1.0
Authors: Mirjam Luijten, Robert Barouki, et al.	Page: 41

12. In the interpretation of results from the Hazard Index in a tiered approach, sufficient attention should be given to the underlying uncertainties in the applied assessment factors for the substance-specific Hazard Quotients used in the Hazard Index.
13. In the risk assessment and management of mixtures, chemicals from other sources, e.g. medication or recreational drugs, that produce similar adverse outcomes, should also be taken into account to the degree possible. A legal basis to do so needs to be further developed.
14. The identification of groups of co-occurring substances, regulated in different domains and sector, and of toxicological concern, as through network analysis and mixture risk assessment, underscores the need to strengthen mixture risk assessment across regulatory domains and sectors.